

Challenges and Opportunities of Young Entrepreneurs

Dr.M.Murugeswari

Assistant Professor of Commerce

Sri Parasakthi College for Women (Autonomous), Courtallam

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Abstract

Recently, awareness in youth entrepreneurship has been fuelled due to high levels of unemployment amongst young people and as a way to promote employment opportunities or to address social exclusion. Youth entrepreneurship has gained more importance in recent years in many countries, with increased interest in entrepreneurship as a way of boosting economic competitiveness and promoting regional development. Based on survey and interview of the young entrepreneurs through a structured questionnaire in Tirunelveli, the researchers have made an effort to study the factors contributing to the promotion of young entrepreneurs to start up their own enterprise, to find out the constraints that impedes and prospects that motivates the young people in starting and running a business and to assess the performance of the young entrepreneurs in Tirunelveli.

Keywords: Youth entrepreneurship, Economic development, Unemployment.

Introduction

The role of entrepreneurship plays in the socio-economic development of a country is well acknowledged. As a result, a large number of programmes to support entrepreneurship to execute its economic and societal roles designed by the governments and international organizations. However, due to the awareness that the concepts of entrepreneurship and youth entrepreneurship are identical, youth entrepreneurship remain somewhat unaddressed in many countries while considerable attention has been made upon entrepreneurship in general. The problems of entrepreneurship have been addressed in the same way for different groups within the population by the use of ‘one size fits all’ policies and programmes. In recent times, interest in youth entrepreneurship has been fuelled due to high levels of unemployment amongst young people and as a way to promote employment opportunities or to address social exclusion. Furthermore, entrepreneurship is seen as a channel for the talents of many highly educated young people in areas such as information technology, biotechnology and other modern industries. Youth entrepreneurship has gained more importance in recent years in many countries with increased interest in entrepreneurship as a way of boosting economic competitiveness and promoting regional development. While youth entrepreneurship is an under-explored field in academic and policy debates, two main factors account for its growing attention in developed countries. The first is the increased

number of unemployed young people compared to the rest of the population; the second is the need for greater competitiveness, and the accompanying pressures for skills development and entrepreneurship as a way of addressing the pressures of globalization. In general terms youth unemployment is connected to: firstly, the difficult transition from school to work; secondly, the unwillingness of employers to employ inexperienced workers, and; thirdly, the frequent job changes by young people in an attempt to find a satisfactory job (United Nations, 2003). Although the literature on youth entrepreneurship is limited, there is evidence (Greene, 2005) that young people think that working for themselves as a career option since it offers them an interesting job, freedom and autonomy which other

Promotion of youth entrepreneurship in the state will not only quicken the pace of economic development but will allow the youth to utilize and make best use of their potentialities and will also solve the problem of spiraling unemployment. Entrepreneur and Entrepreneurship has been defined by various authors in various ways. Peter Drucker defines it as one who always searches for change, respond to it and exploit it as an opportunity. Innovation is a specific tool of entrepreneur, the means by which they exploit change as an opportunity for a different business / service. According to Schumpeter, an entrepreneur is a person who is willing and able to convert a new idea or invention into a successful innovation. Entrepreneurship employs what Schumpeter called “the gale of creative destruction” to replace in whole or in part inferior innovations across markets and industries, simultaneously creating new products including new business models. In general terms an entrepreneur is one who creates and establishes a new endeavor by analyzing prospect for profit/growth, as well as endows his/ her majority of the time and resources to make it his/her principal source of earning. For the purpose of this paper, ‘youth’ has been defined as a person between 18-35 years of age and a youth entrepreneur is defined as the entrepreneur with in the age group 18 – 35 years.

Objectives and Methodology

- To study the factors contributing to the promotion of young entrepreneurs to start up their own enterprise.
- To analyze the constraints that obstructs and prospects that motivates the young people from starting and running a business Tirunelveli Dist.

The study is based on an exploratory research of 120 young entrepreneurs from the cities of Bhubaneswar and Cuttack. For undertaking the survey, a structured questionnaire was prepared which covered different issues relating to the social and economic background of entrepreneurs, motivating factors for entrepreneurship, problems faced by the entrepreneurs’ and the like. Secondary data, i.e., through websites, books and journals were also referred for the preparation of the research article. The sample young entrepreneurs in Tirunelveli were drawn by using a multi stage cluster sampling method.

Data Analysis

Characteristics of enterprise and entrepreneur

It was found that around 44 percent of the enterprises have 5 to 10 years of existence whereas 27 percent of the enterprises have 0-5 years of existence. The sample reveals that around 92 percent of the enterprises belonged to the category of small enterprises. 79 percent of the enterprises are selling consumer products, 15 percent industrial whereas only 6 percent are into intermediate selling. Nearly 88 percent of the enterprise sold their products in the local market, 11 percent in other districts and 1 percent in villages. Out of the total enterprise 87 percent are sole proprietors whereas 13 percent are into partnership form of business. 76 percent of the enterprise established

their enterprise in market place whereas 16percent and 8percent established their enterprises at their home and industrial area respectively. The characteristics of the sample entrepreneurs, revealed that 57 percent of the respondents belonged to joint family whereas 43 percent belonged to nuclear family. Around 73 percent of the respondents hailed from business origin and 27 percent from non business origin. Out of the total respondents 97 percent are male entrepreneurs and only 3 percent are female entrepreneurs. 69percent respondents are married whereas 31percent are unmarried Nearly 42 percent of the respondents are graduate, 29 percent under graduate, 18 percent matriculates and 11 percent post graduates. About 60 percent have average academic performance, 37 percent good and 3 percent poor academic performance. 84 percent belonged to middle class family, 14 percent upper class and 2 percent of the respondents are from lower class. A majority of respondents i.e., 75 percent are from business family, 24 percent service and 1 percent from agriculture family. 70 percent of the respondents have no prior working experience whereas 30 percent have few years of working experience.

Sources of Idea to Establishing the Enterprise

Table 1 Sources of Idea to Establishing the Enterprise

Sl. No.	Sources of Idea to Establishing the Enterprise	Frequency	Percentage
1	Friends and Relatives	35	29
2	Media Coverage of Business and Business People	30	25
3	Ideas Received from Training Programme	26	22
4	Career Advisers	19	16
5	Others	10	8

Starting a new business means having a business idea translated into a concrete and structured business plan. Future entrepreneurs will first of all need to evaluate the feasibility of the entrepreneurial idea through a careful analysis of the product and of its reference market. Through the sample survey it was found that around 29 percent of the respondent got the idea of setting up the enterprise through their friends and relatives, 8percent from other sources like market study, own idea, father and the like, followed by media i.e., 25 percent, training programmes and advisors 16percent and 22 percent each. Two case studies revealed that the entrepreneur that they got idea of establishing the enterprise from market survey and from relatives. Reason for choosing entrepreneurship as careers many people opt for entrepreneurship as their career because of many reasons.

Reasons of Choosing Entrepreneurship as a Career

Some delve into the industry because they would want to run their own business, answering to no one and setting all the rules and protocols by themselves. Others jump into entrepreneurship because they have seen that most successful people in the world own a successful business. There are also others that make entrepreneurship as a second career because their current jobs are not earning enough for them.

Table 2 Choosing Entrepreneurship as a Career

Sl. No.	Reasons of Choosing Entrepreneurship as a Career	Frequency	Percentage
1	Desire to be Independent	34	28
2	To Create Jobs for Others	15	12

3	Inability to get Desired Jobs	12	10
4	Dislike for the Previous Job / Employer	16	13
5	To Earn more Money	28	23
6	To Manage family Business	15	13

From the sample research it was found that nearly half of the sample i.e., 28 percent of the respondents chose entrepreneurship as a career because they have the desire to be independent while 23 percent want to earn more money, 13 percent of the respondents have to manage their family business. Both the entrepreneurs in the case study said that they desired to be independent and wanted to earn more money

Barriers and Obstacles in Start up of Business

The success or failure of an enterprise is often dependent on overcoming a series of potential barriers, e.g. securing sufficient financial backing, adequate and appropriate guidance and training etc

Table 3 Barriers and Obstacles in Start up of Business

Variables	Total Score	Rank
Social / Cultural Attitude	560	VI
Access To Finance	120	I
Govt Regulations	150	II
Education, Skill & Training	430	V
Business Support	380	IV
Marketing of goods	260	III

From the sample survey it was found that a majority of I respondents ranked access to finance as the important area where they faced obstacle to engage in business, whereas II ranked government regulation as the area of obstacle, III percent ranked business support as the major area of difficulty in startups. The two case studies revealed that lack of adequate access to finance and business support was the obstacles faced in start up of the enterprise.

Regulative Barriers

Table 4 Regulative Barrier

Sl. No	Regulative Barriers	Over All	F Value	P Value
1	Tax Rates	2.13	4.673	.003
2	Subsidy Policy	2.98	7.664	.007
3	Trade Policy	2.92	9.458	.004
4	Others	4.02	10.161	.002

As shown in the above table it was found from the sample survey that tax rates, subsidy policy, trade policy and few other taxation regulations are the regulative problems faced by the young entrepreneurs. Tax rates were the major regulative barrier according to the sample case studies taken.

Important De-Motivators (Fears) to Engage in Business**Table 5 Important De-Motivators (Fears) to Engage in Business**

Sl. No.	Fears / De motivators	Over All	F Value	P Value
1	Financial Risk	3.43	9.740	0.002
2	Access to Finance	3.07	0.754	0.387
3	Social Risks	3.08	0.969	0.327
4	Lack of skills	2.92	0.303	0.583
5	Administrative Hurdles	3.14	0.278	0.599
6	Stigma associated with failing	3.34	2.188	0.142
7	Workload	2.89	0.068	0.795
8	Corruption	2.95	1.049	0.308
9	Competition	3.48	0.992	0.322
10	Market Demand	3.78	3.438	0.067

It was found that financial risk had a significant impact & is considered to be an important de-motivating factor for young entrepreneurs in setting up an enterprise.

Emphasis Lay Upon By the Family**Table 6 Emphasis Lay Upon By the Family**

Sl. No.	Family Environment	Over All	F Value	P Value
1	Education	2.45	3.796	0.054
2	Adventure	2.79	11.266	0.001
3	Honesty	2.23	6.538	0.012
4	Religion	1.92	1.661	0.201
5	Innovation	2.69	2.021	0.158
6	Learning	2.23	6.538	0.012
7	Independent	2.24	1.847	0.177
8	Openness	2.69	1.379	0.243
9	Doing Business	2.23	0.308	0.580
10	Hard Work	1.88	3.549	0.063

From the sample it was found that education, adventure and learning are some factors / areas on which the families emphasized. The two case studies revealed that their family laid emphasis on honesty, religion, independent, doing business and hard work

Conclusion

The survey exposed that most of the young entrepreneurs even though had other occupational opportunities chose entrepreneurship as a career because they seek to be independent and to earn more money. The majority of the young entrepreneurs in Tirunelveli suffer from the problem of shortage of working capital, tax regulations and lack of adequate encouragement by the society. These have been the curse for poor performance in the state, contrary to the belief that does not have indigenous, dynamic and committed entrepreneurs. Today, youth is more daring and hardworking and career oriented, and can be easily transformed if proper training and knowledge in entrepreneurship can be provided. The cultivation of the new breed is in our hands and we have to stand-in their requirements with their skill and entrepreneurship orientation and perception enhancement for better Tirunelveli and India. Entrepreneurship can be more commended if we can submit the transformation process of the youth which had started in our nation and could live long and continue if more doors can be opened in their support because they are going to be entrepreneurial citizens of tomorrow.